

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

HYBRID RICE

Retardation of heading in male sterile and restorer lines using paclobutrazol

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Flowering synchronization in parent plants is a key problem in increasing

hybrid rice seed yields. Heading can be promoted by GA₃ treatment, but no one has reported delay in heading by growth regulators.

We sprayed an aqueous solution of 75 ppm paclobutrazol at 11 ml/m² on rice plants at the pollen mother cell formation stage of a cytoplasmic male sterile line (Zhen Shan 97A) and a

restorer line (IR64) growing in the field. Endogenous GA₃ content was determined by leaf sheath bioassay.

Paclobutrazol treatment reduced endogenous GA₃ content in panicles (paclobutrazol is an anti-gibberellin). After treatment, elongating rate of the topmost internode decreased. Beginning of heading was delayed 2-4 d with 1 treatment and 4-6 d with a second treatment 5 d after the first treatment (Table 1).

Foliar spray of GA₃ solution counteracted the retardative effect of paclobutrazol and the plants recovered their height or were even taller (Table 2). The pollen in treated plants developed normally, so did the seeds of the treated and the next generation.

Using paclobutrazol spray at panicle differentiation could adjust synchronization of flowering in male sterile lines and pollen parents and should be conducive to higher crossed seed set. □

Table 1. Effect of 75 ppm paclobutrazol solution on the heading of cytoplasmic male sterile line and restorer line of rice, Guangzhou, China, 1985-86.

Line	Sowing date	Treatment date	Beginning of heading ^a	
			Control	Treated
Restorer line				
IR64	11 Mar 1985	4 Jun	14 Jun	16 Jun
IR64	3 Jul 1986	30 Aug	8 Sep	10 Sep
Cytoplasmic male sterile line				
Zhen Shan 97A	12 Apr 1985	2 Jun	12 Jun	15 Jun
Zhen Shan 97A	17 Jul 1986	4 Sep	14 Sep	18 Sep
Zhen Shan 97A	7 Apr 1986	29 May ^b	9 Jun	12 Jun
Zhen Shan 97A	7 Apr 1986	29 May ^c	9 Jun	15 Jun
		3 Jun ^d		

^a 10% of the panicles have exerted. ^b First treatment, no second treatment. ^c First treatment. ^d Second treatment.

Table 2. Effect of paclobutrazol (Pac) and GA₃ on internode length^a of mature rice plant Zhen Shan 97A, Guangzhou, China, 1986.

Treatment	Topmost internode	2d internode		3d internode		4th internode		1-4 internodes			
		Length (cm)	%	Length (cm)	%	Length (cm)	%	Length (cm)	%		
0	0	20.0 b	100	13.0 b	100	7.1 b	100	3.4 b	100	43.4 b	100
75 ppm Pac	0	16.6 c	83	12.9 c	84	6.6 b	93	3.4 b	100	37.5 c	83
75 ppm Pac	75 ppm Pac	10.2 d	51	6.5 d	50	6.0 b	84	2.8 b	83	25.8 d	59
75 ppm Pac	30 ppm GA ₃	20.2 b	101	13.3 b	102	6.9 b	97	3.0 b	90	43.4 b	100
75 ppm Pac	50 ppm GA ₃	22.5 a	112	23.1 a	178	25.2 a	354	11.3 a	337	82.1 a	189

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test. ^b Conducted at pollen mother cell formation stage.

Evaluation and use of male sterile systems in Mekong Delta, Vietnam

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We evaluated in 1983-86 10 male sterile (A) lines and their corresponding maintainer (B) lines introduced from

China and IRRI.

A and B lines were transplanted in a row ratio of 2:4. Sowing times were adjusted to synchronize flowering. Seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing and received 70-40-30 kg NPK/ha. Rope pulling was used to supplement cross pollination but flag leaves were not clipped and GA₃ was not applied.

Agronomic traits and disease and insect reactions were recorded. Percentage spikelet sterility was determined by bagging five panicles from three plants of each A line at heading in the greenhouse. To estimate outcrossing pollination rate, 20 plants were harvested.

V20A, V41A, Zhen Shan 97A, and Yar ai zhao A did not perform well in